

WP1 – Milestone 2

Input to Roadmap - WP1 Synthesis and gap analysis framework

Water-ForCE

Project Identification

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Table of Contents

1. Objective	4
2. Water sector	5
User categories	5
Market Drivers	7
EU, International policy and SDG drivers	8
Technology Drivers	11
Growing trend for CS	12
3. Water sector EO value chain	13
4. Stakeholder identification	16
Gathering of user requirements	17
5. User requirements results	19
6. Public domain and EU policies	21
7. Contribution towards societal challenges, missions and SDGs	24
8. Links between mission-service application	28
9. Innovation needs and business opportunities	35
10. Conclusions and recommendations to the Roadmap	39
11. Framework to identify gaps between EO and user requirements	43

1. Objective

The main objective of this MS2 document is to summarise the findings of WP1 as input to the development of a Roadmap for the Inland water sector in WP6.

Here we have highlighted the essential messages from the research carried out for WP1 on the links between stakeholders, policies and Copernicus missions and services to be able to draw conclusions on the gaps in meeting user requirements, the innovation needs and business opportunities as well as Copernicus' contribution to the SDGs. Besides offering a summary of the work undertaken in each of the six tasks, we have also considered the 'representativeness' of the stakeholder analysis, and interviews. In addition, we focus on the elucidation of all the user requirements including those obtained from user interviews, and the analysis of EU policies and global SDGs. Finally, we present a framework that will highlight any gaps in the analysis, and especially the extent to which the user requirements (from D1.3 and D1.4) can be met by EO data and Copernicus services.

The structure of this document was guided by the tasks of WP1 (but not necessarily in the same order) and the deliverables in which these topics were addressed, viz.

- 1) Value chain and stakeholder identification (D1.1, D1.5)
- 2) Public domain and business sector identification (D1.2)
- 3) Links between mission-service applications (D1.3)
- 4) End user needs and requirements identification (D1.4)
- 5) Innovation need and opportunities (D1.5)
- 6) Contributions towards societal challenges, missions and SDGs (D1.6)

2. Water sector

User categories

The sectors identified in WaterForce WP1 include:

- Drinking water management
- Aquaculture/fisheries
- Agriculture
- Urban water management
- River basin management
- Hazards/Emergencies
- Coastal zone management
- Biodiversity
- Energy
- Policy/regulator
- Research
- EO service providers

With regard to thematic sectors, D1.5 also considered those specified in Water Europe (2017¹) which identifies five main user groups of inland water - Industry, Agriculture, Homes, Service and recreation (including tourism), and Nature. According to this report, the main water users in Europe are:

- Agriculture (40%)
- Energy (28%)
- Mining and manufacturing (18%)

¹ Water Europe, 2017. [The Value of Water: Multiple Waters for Multiple purposes and Users. Towards a Future-Proof Model for a European Water-Smart Society](#)

- Household use (12%)

Looking at aquatic systems, the main sources of freshwater water (for drinking and other uses) are from:

- rivers and groundwater (88.2 %)
- reservoirs (10.3 %)
- lakes (1.5 %).

Thus, from a water industry perspective, the key stakeholders are the agricultural sector and energy producers, while river basin managers are key from a freshwater supply point of view.

From an economic perspective, recreation and tourism (bathing sites, water sports, etc.) is very important to the economies of many European countries. Travel and tourism comprises an average of 13% of GDP across the EU 28 in 2020², part of which relates to water bodies (lakes, coastal zones, etc.). The hazards and emergencies sector is also economically significant due to the huge costs of damage due to droughts and floods. According to the EEA, climate-related hazards, such as heavy precipitation and droughts, lead to economic losses totalling an estimated EUR 487 billion in the EU-27 Member States between 1980 and 2020³. In addition, the Biodiversity sector is becoming more and more important from an environmental perspective (also reflected by the new EU Green Deal), and although it hasn't been valued yet, estimating the 'monetary value' of nature is the focus of ongoing research⁴.

As pointed out in D1.5, a significant difference between the water applications listed in Water Europe (2017⁵) and those analysed from an EO perspective (in D1.4) is the exclusion

²<https://www.statista.com/statistics/1228395/travel-and-tourism-share-of-gdp-in-the-eu-by-country/>

³ <https://www.eea.europa.eu/ims/economic-losses-from-climate-related>

⁴ https://ec.europa.eu/environment/nature/biodiversity/economics/index_en.htm

⁵ Water Europe, 2017. [*The Value of Water: Multiple Waters for Multiple purposes and Users. Towards a Future-Proof Model for a European Water-Smart Society*](#)

of marine related sectors, such as Aquaculture/fisheries and Coastal zone management. However, we have retained these sectors in our analysis as they are important from an economic perspective - according to Eurostat, in 2018 EU aquaculture production was worth €4 billion.

Keeping all this in mind, a number of user sectors can be prioritised according to their demand for data and information on water:

- Agriculture (biggest user sector and increasing compliance demand from new Common Agricultural Policy, Groundwater Directive, etc.)
- Energy (large user sector with economic importance)
- River basin and drinking water managers, and national water agencies responsible for collating data for the EU Directives
- Hazards and emergencies (with consequences of large economic losses)
- Tourism and Biodiversity (with its links to Bathing Water Directive, coastal zone management, European Green Deal, Biodiversity Strategy, Habitats Directive, etc.)

Market Drivers

The overall size of the global water market is vast (valued at €62.9 trillion by Water Europe 2017⁶), as are the challenges faced by 'Water use in Europe - quantity and quality face big challenges (EEA 2018⁷).

In 2016, Water Europe - a European Technology Platform for Water - drew up a Vision document (Water Europe 2017) for the future of the water sector, and to tackle the pressing issues faced by Europe. This document suggests a paradigm shift in the industry towards a water-smart society that reflects the true economic value of water. This is

⁶ Water Europe, 2017. [The Value of Water: Multiple Waters for Multiple purposes and Users, Towards a Future-Proof Model for a European Water-Smart Society](#)

⁷ EEA, 2018. [Water use in Europe – Quantity and quality face big challenges](#)

enabled by new *'digital water technologies'*, as novel technologies and strategies will be needed to optimise the management of our water resources. Currently Europe is lacking in detailed water management information, and there is a pressing need to increase the level of monitoring of the quality and quantity of water availability and use. GIS-based knowledge management systems with active measuring and monitoring technologies, will support better decision making, especially at regional and supra-regional levels.

It is in these areas of digital technologies and GIS-based management information that EO could support the water sector, together with in-situ technologies like smart sensors, drones, etc. The wide coverage of EO facilitates environmental monitoring and cross-border management of rivers, lakes, reservoirs, etc. EO also enables cross-sector monitoring such as water and energy, water and agriculture, or water and hazards. Such decision making systems should use multi-source analytics in conjunction with EO and work towards systems for situational awareness in water management. Customers would like seamless links between the information from EO, drones, citizen science and in-situ monitoring. This is now enabled by the move to digital technologies and developments in smart sensors, IoT, big data analytics, AI, etc.

EU, International policy and SDG drivers

Business innovation opportunities in the inland water sector are highly influenced by policy and legislative actions within the EU and intergovernmental organisations, which follows from the analysis in Water-ForCE deliverable D.1.3. Thus, the market for water information is driven by the EU Space Programme Regulation itself, but also by EU sectoral policies, international treaties, resolutions, and other guiding instruments.

Under the Space Programme Regulation (EU) 2021/696, acceptable activities for Copernicus and its services must include novel use cases for water management, as well as inland water quality and quantity monitoring. As a result, making open-source platforms

accessible and understandable to end-users is crucial for ensuring successful policy implementation through better decision-making. The Water Framework Directive (WFD), as the key policy driver for inland water monitoring, does not explicitly mention space methods of monitoring, but calls for more effective methods for water quality and quantity monitoring. As also found by the comparative analysis of WFD methods in Water-ForCE deliverable D.1.3, indicators derived from EO data greatly supplement routine sampling while significantly expanding geographical and temporal coverage, particularly in bigger bodies of water. Besides the water sector, inland water management is inextricably tied to agricultural and environmental policies, which also drive Copernicus uptake. See Table 1 for a complete list of EC Directives and Regulation related to the water sector.

A new feature of the Horizon Europe research and innovation programme (2021-2027), are the EU Missions Initiatives. Inland water management falls at the Mission Area “Healthy Oceans, Seas, and Coastal and Inland Waters”. It asserts that Europe will demonstrate worldwide leadership in managing transboundary inland waters by 2030 in order to protect climate-resilient water ecosystems. Inland water management is critical to ecosystem resilience to climate change, hence comprehensive monitoring of their status is critical. Simultaneously, forests and wetlands have a direct impact on inland waterways, allowing ecosystems to deal with fast change, absorb excess rainfall or drought, preserve biodiversity, and absorb carbon. As a result, it is necessary to monitor not just the bodies of water themselves, but also the ecosystems that impact them, such as forests. Thus, satellite imagery and other Earth observation tools are cited in the Water Mission Paper as a driver of research and innovation in this field, as they provide new insights into the water supply in parts of the world where traditional land-based methods of measuring water supply are not possible or practical.

Water is also a significant matter for international action, with a number of intergovernmental treaties and recommendations in place. Key international treaties obliging to implement monitoring measures in the domains which concern inland waters are:

- Convention on the Protection and Use of Transboundary Watercourses and International Lakes (Water Convention) of 1992
- Convention on wetlands of international importance especially as waterfowl habitat (Ramsar Convention) of 1971
- Convention on Biological Diversity of 1992

Though there are no legal obligations in such documents, they are still of high political value. There are also international instruments in the inland water management domain, many of which directly refer to the use of space technologies (see D1.3), such as:

- the Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction 2015-2030,
- UN Environmental Programme (UNEP) Resolution 3/10 'Addressing water pollution to protect and restore water-related ecosystems' of 2018,
- the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, Guidelines for safe recreational water environments 2003,
- the Intergovernmental Hydrological Programme (IHP-IX), World Bank Strategic Plans.

The analysis in D1.6 identified 12 of the UN Sustainable Development Goals as having parameters specific for the inland water quality and quantity that could be monitored by EO (see Table 2). This highlights the relevance of EO capabilities towards achieving the SDG targets by 2030, and demonstrates the need for broad spatial scale and fine temporal resolution global monitoring of inland waters to achieve the SDGs. Moreover, IHE demonstrated that current increasing temporal and spatial resolution data availability together with continuous data sets for various water resources and improved data reliability, also greatly contribute to the development of opportunities for water quantity monitoring. In addition, with more and more data sets becoming open access, all

necessary measurements can be accessed near real time and the information can be used retrospectively.⁸

Technology Drivers

Artificial Intelligence (AI), cybersecurity, Internet of Things (IoT), Big Data, High Performance Computing, 5G, and Software are the main digital specialisations for Europe's digital transformation by 2030 ([Europe's Digital Decade](#), 2021).

With respect to EO and the water sector, there are a number of technologies that will drive market uptake:

- AI-based big-data analysis bears the promises to revolutionise the use of satellite data by allowing to ingest and process huge amounts of information at once. Other AI applications to EO include data processing, change detection, object recognition, identification, prediction and so on. Deep learning (DL), a subset of Machine Learning (ML), uses multilayered neural networks and extracts features and patterns from raw data.
- Another important area of application is to build predictive tools which involve statistical models collecting third-party data, such as geostatistical information on the environment. Though, these are still in the early stage of development.
- Cloud computing enables EO service providers to offer lower-cost services based on the web, bypassing in this way for their customers mounting infrastructure (hardware and software) costs or maintenance and paying only for the services which are provided.

⁸ Marloes Mul, Water Accounting plus using remote sensing for monitoring SDG 6 <https://files.lobelia.earth/web-waterforce/webinar-wa4sdgs-waterforce.pdf>; see also IHE Delft Water Accounting Project <https://www.un-ihe.org/water-accounting-project-website> (<https://www.wateraccounting.org/>).

- New business models that can be implemented as part of the EO for Water value chain building on the capabilities of cloud computing:
 - Infrastructure as a Service (IaaS) where users outsource data storage, network and operating system management;
 - Platform as a Service (PaaS) which provides access to large volumes of historical data and sometimes API (Application Programming Interface) allowing developers to create new applications;
 - Data as a Service (DaaS) which allows easy access through a web based interface or a GIS plugin to proprietary up-to-date and third-party data with analytics tools (e.g. Copernicus DIAS);
 - Software as a Service (SaaS) when users can access software applications through a web based interface or deployed behind a proprietary firewall to access information.

Growing trend for Citizen science

Citizen science (CS; also known as community science, crowd science, crowd-sourced science, civic science, or volunteer monitoring) refers to data collected by citizens or community groups for scientific research. CS can also be described as "public participation in scientific research", participatory monitoring or action research, that can improve the scientific community's capacity, as well as involving the public and increase their understanding of science. There is a growing trend to utilise CS with the environmental monitoring domain. Within Europe, over 16 countries are actively involved in running some type of environmental citizen observatory.

Citizen or crowd science projects related to water include:

- FreshWaterWatch is a global CS project from Earthwatch Europe (earthwatch.org). The aim of FreshWaterWatch (freshwaterwatch.thewaterhub.org) is to ensure that citizens across the globe can monitor the health of the lakes, rivers, streams, wetlands and reservoirs. Using FreshWaterWatch kits, citizens can measure water quality (including nitrate and phosphate levels, turbidity, and visual factors) and the results are reported on the world-wide data repository (freshwaterwatch.thewaterhub.org/our-data/explore-our-data).
- The [Monocle project](#) is investigating the complementarity of CS and in-situ monitoring, and the role citizens and communities can play in the maintenance and deployment of sensors.
- CS campaigns such as: [Eye On Water](#), [Seen-monitoring in Europe](#), [The Secchi-Dip In in North America](#), and State level efforts for citizen science focusing on freshwater in [Minnesota](#), [Wisconsin](#), [Michigan](#), and [Maine](#)

These examples show that citizen or crowd science activities can make a valuable contribution to water monitoring, as part of in-situ measurements, to complement information derived from EO. In a recent EEA Report (Oct 2021) that focused on the lake water quality in-situ data requirements and availability, the potential of citizen science data to support cal-val of satellite EO water quality products was recognised.

3. Water sector EO value chain

An expanded EO chain for the water sector was developed in D1.5 (based on the methodology followed in the EUSPA EO and GNSS Market report), which includes 6 levels:

- Infrastructure providers: providers of various types of computing infrastructure upon which EO data can be accessed, stored, distributed or manipulated.
- Data providers: providers of unprocessed or pre-processed EO data.

- Platform providers: providers of online platforms and/or digital services, through which users can utilise tools and capabilities to analyse EO data, develop algorithms and build applications.
- EO products and service providers: providers of products (e.g. land cover classifications) or services (e.g. ground motion monitoring) that make full use of EO data and processing capabilities offered by data and platform providers.
- Information providers: providers of sector-specific information that incorporates EO data along with non-EO data.
- End Users: the final users who benefit from the applications and services offered by information providers.

This is illustrated in the diagram below and includes the names of public offerings and private companies operating in the sector (non-exhaustive).

Figure 3: The EO Value Chain for the inland water sector based on EUSPA's EO market report (2022) and Water-ForCE expert interviews

4. Stakeholder identification

D1.1 lists the 155 individual stakeholders that were registered at that time in the project’s database HubSpot, representing 105 unique organisations/institutions/companies. The breakdown according to active sector can be seen in Figure 1 (107 stakeholders excluding the research and EO service providers), and it can be seen that it includes a wide range of key user sectors. The River basin and drinking water management sector (urban water and water utility) are well represented (total of 29.9%), as is the hazards and emergencies sector (15%), but the agriculture, energy and tourism/recreational sectors are underrepresented at 7.5%, 1.9% and 1.9% respectively. It was also noted that few representatives from private industry (such as mining and manufacturing) attended the workshops or have signed up to HubSpot.

Figure 1: Stakeholders according to active sectors: percentage of total number of active sectors listed (n=107)

Figure 2: Stakeholders according to aquatic system: Percentage of total number of aquatic systems listed (n=80)

Considering the aquatic systems, Figure 2 shows a good representation of stakeholders across all the systems.

Since this analysis, carried out in early 2021, the number of registrations on HubSpot has increased significantly to over 600. However, for the purposes of the end-user needs and requirements analysis (reported in D1.4), these first registrations represent the sample group.

Gathering of user requirements

As mentioned above, the elucidation of the user requirements was based on around 152 interviews (during a number of workshops and project meetings). The breakdown of requests by user sector is shown in the table below:

User sector	<i>Number of user requirements expressed</i>
Drinking water management	21
Aquaculture/fisheries	7
Agriculture	15
Urban water management	22
River basin management	37
Hazards/Emergencies	16
Coastal zone management	12
Biodiversity	10
Energy	5
Policy (across all sectors)	6

On review of the user requirements, members of the WaterForCE team have pointed out that the sensing and monitoring of water QUANTITY has not sufficiently been covered and that this needs to be addressed.

It was not the aim of the WaterForCE project to carry out a fully comprehensive stakeholder analysis. Nevertheless, it can be noted that there are a number of sector gaps in our analysis, according to their water usage:

- agriculture

- energy
- tourism and recreation
- private industry (such as mining and manufacturing)

5. User requirements results

Under task 1.4, a large number of emerging user needs were identified across the application areas (and reported in D1.4). These are listed here following prioritisation (carried out in D1.5) according to the number of user requests (from high to low):

1. Water quality and water levels (quantity) not only on major lakes, but also in smaller reservoirs and rivers and much finer scale (catchment scale). The need for such information has been identified by most of the experts and organisations interviewed for this report (see interviews summary above)
2. Inclusion of microbial, toxin, algal and metal indicators and plastic pollution indicators. Dashboards or early warning systems for algal blooms and cyanobacteria are recurrently identified also in the experts interviews.
3. Watershed modelling, hydrological and hydrodynamic modelling
4. Detection of dissolved organic matter
5. Chlorophyll-a concentration in lakes and inland waters in general. NIOO-KNAW's water ecology department is currently conducting exploratory research in order to test the feasibility of using EO data for monitoring Chlorophyll-a concentration in lakes and rivers.
6. Coupling groundwater level monitoring to land use change
7. Discrimination of permanent and temporary water bodies
8. Risk-related indices to water systems: congestion, fishing jetties, flow speed, overgrowth, subsidence, sedimentation.

9. Monitoring of fast growing water plants and algae. NIOO-KNAW received a request from the Dutch National Water Authority to map the vegetation growth that could hinder vessels movement on inland waterways.
10. Better resolution of the algal community structure and biomass
11. Hydrological models to calculate hydrological fluxes for small streams or entire river basins in connection with sea
12. Information to monitor ground-water aquifers
13. Dedicated services for water level, altimetry, bathymetry
14. Inland waterways, canals, ditches, culverts. RoyalDHV has developed a prototype for monitoring small canals, ditches and inland waterways for vegetation growth (e.g., duckweed) and dredging sludges
15. Detect leakage from supply network
16. Soil moisture/soil water balance (observations and forecasts)
17. Service for evapotranspiration process (observations and forecasts)
18. Frequent mapping of CDOM (coloured dissolved organic matter)/DOC (dissolved organic carbon) products to assist on drinking water quality monitoring
19. Monitoring service for drinking water quantity and quality. Parameters such as a) cyanobacterial harmful algal blooms, b) Frequency of algal bloom occurrence. NIOO-KNAW is monitoring (though only in-situ at the moment) the drinking water quality for water resources management companies. Presently, the institute is investigating the possibility to use EO products and services for the same objectives
20. Regular information on river dynamics and especially river runoff, interfaces with seas/oceans and overall hydrological dynamics
21. Water-related forecasts and water-related climate record
22. Floods and droughts forecasting and monitoring. Near 'real time' forecasts. The EO Provider we interviewed has indicated a new upcoming market sector for the EO, the insurance companies which requests more and more data for mapping and assessing floods damages

23. Detection of soil salinization
24. Forecast models and provision of early warning for food production and sustainable agriculture
25. Monitoring of drinking water quality in reservoirs
26. Sea Surface temperature in coastal and inland water
27. Basin-scale high resolution surface models and topography data
28. Services dedicated to coastal areas.

These identified evolving user needs for new products and services correlate well with the views expressed by industry experts (reported in D1.5). However, this list should only be considered as a first indication of the applications that are important to the water sector as the analysis might be skewed by the selection of interviewees.

6. Public domain and EU policies

From a regulatory perspective, the EU is a major stakeholder with around 20 directives regarding the quality and use of water. This creates a strong demand pull for data on water from all possible sources, including EO (even if this is not explicitly stipulated in the policy texts - as investigated in D1.2). Task 1.3 identified 20 EC Directives and regulations that are linked to water and these are summarised in the table below.

Table 1: List of EC Directives and Regulation related to the water sector

	Long Name	Short Name
1	Water Framework Directive (WFD) 2000/60/EC (consolidated in 2014)	Water Framework Directive
2	Directive 2008/105/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 16 December 2008 on environmental quality standards in the field of water policy	Environmental Quality Standards Directive

	Long Name	Short Name
3	Directive 2006/118/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 12 December 2006 on the protection of groundwater against pollution and deterioration	Groundwater Directive
4	Directive 2007/60/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 October 2007 on the assessment and management of flood risks	Floods Directive
5	Council Directive 91/271/EEC of 21 May 1991 concerning urban waste-water treatment (consolidated in 2014)	Urban Waste Water Treatment Directive
6	Council Directive 91/676/EEC concerning the protection of waters against pollution caused by nitrates from agricultural sources (consolidated in 2008)	Nitrates Directive
7	Directive 2010/75/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 24 November 2010 on industrial emissions (integrated pollution prevention and control) (consolidated in 2011)	Industrial Emissions Directive
8	Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions NAIADES III: Boosting future-proof European inland waterway transport (COM/2021/324)	Inland Waterway Transport Action Plan
9	Directive 2006/7/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 15 February 2006 concerning the management of bathing water quality and repealing Directive 76/160/EEC	Bathing Water Directive
10	Regulation (EU) 2020/741 on minimum requirements for water reuse	Water Reuse Directive
11	Proposal for a REGULATION OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL establishing rules on support for strategic plans to be drawn up by Member States under the Common agricultural policy (CAP Strategic Plans) and financed by the European Agricultural Guarantee Fund (EAGF) and by the European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD) and repealing Regulation (EU) No 1305/2013 of the European Parliament and of the Council and Regulation (EU) No 1307/2013 of the European Parliament and of the Council (COM/2018/392)	Proposal for Common agricultural policy

	Long Name	Short Name
12	EU Regulation 2021/2116, repealing EU Regulation 1306/2013 on the financing, management and monitoring of the CAP	CAP Management Regulation
13	EU Regulation 2021/2115, establishing rules on support for national CAP strategic plans and repealing EU Regulations 1305/2013 on support for rural development and 1307/2013 on rules for direct payments to farmers	CAP Strategic Plans Regulation
14	EU Regulation 2021/2117, amending EU Regulations 1308/2013 on the common organisation of the agricultural markets, 1151/2012 on quality schemes for agricultural products, 251/2014 on geographical indications for aromatised wine products, and 228/2013 laying down measures for agriculture in the outermost regions of the EU	Agricultural Markets Regulation
15	Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the European Council, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the regions: The European Green Deal (COM/2019/640)	European Green Deal
16	A new Circular Economy Action Plan For a cleaner and more competitive Europe (COM/2020/98)	Circular Economy Action Plan
17	Directive 92/43/EEC (consolidated in 2013) on the conservation of natural habitats and of wild fauna and flora	Habitats Directive
18	Biodiversity Strategy for 2030 'Bringing nature back into our lives' (COM/2020/380)	Biodiversity Strategy 2030
19	Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the regions Pathway to a Healthy Planet for All EU Action Plan: 'Towards Zero Pollution for Air, Water and Soil' (COM/2021/400)	Zero Pollution Action Plan
20	Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council and the European Economic and Social Committee: European Union Strategic Approach to Pharmaceuticals in the Environment (COM/2019/128)	Strategic Approach to Pharmaceuticals

Water is very well represented in EU policy in general, however EO data as a way of monitoring water is present in only a few, even in instruments that came after the Copernicus launch. In EU legislation, policies are interconnected with one contributing and referring to another, with the Water Framework Directive (WFD) as a central part. In other sectors, tightly linked with water use, such as agriculture, new EU policies are developed taking into account availability of satellite imagery which significantly contributes to monitoring efforts. The WFD directive will not be revised, leaving it to future instruments to advise on the monitoring techniques. Notably, current water instruments promoting space technology use are mostly non-binding and do not require compliance from governments. In this realm, it is recommended to lay down certain results that must be achieved but leave each Member State free to decide how to transpose directives into national laws. This also will be in line with the recommendations from WHO not to impede innovations by giving strict prescription on monitoring techniques, but set out the desired results.

7. Contribution towards societal challenges, missions and SDGs

In task 1.6, we have identified links between 12 of the UN Sustainable Development Goals and EO variables for inland water quality and quantity. This highlights the relevance of EO capabilities towards achieving the SDG targets by 2030 and demonstrates the need for broad spatial scale and fine temporal resolution global monitoring of inland waters to achieve the SDGs. The links with all four GCI (Global Climate Indicator) categories with EO variables are also established, demonstrating key ECVs (Essential Climate Variables) that are relevant for inland waters. Table 2 summarises the EO water-related variables that can be exploited in support of SDGs and GCOS (Global CLimate Observing System).

Table 2: Summary of the EO water-related variables that can be exploited in support of SDGs and GCOS

	Category	EO variable
SDGs	SDG1: No poverty	Flood extent, soil moisture
	SDG2: Zero hunger	Water extent, water quality, flood extent, drought, soil moisture
	SDG3: Good health and wellbeing	Algal blooms, water quality
	SDG4: Quality education	Opportunities for exploitation of water related EO-products can be explored
	SDG5: Gender equality	Opportunities for exploitation of water related EO-products can be explored
	SDG6: Clean water and sanitation	Water extent, water quality, aquatic ecosystem
	SDG7: Affordable and clean energy	Clouds, aerosols, wind, river discharge, water extent, water quality, water temperature
	SDG8: Decent work and economic growth	Water quality, water quantity
	SDG9: Industry, innovation and infrastructure	Water level, river flow, stream velocity

	Category	EO variable
	SDG10: Reduced inequalities	Opportunities for exploitation of water related EO-products can be explored
	SDG11: Sustainable cities and communities	Flood extent
	SDG12: Responsible consumption and production	Water quantity, water quality, river discharge
	SDG13: Climate action	Water extent, water temperature, water level, lake ice cover, algal blooms, turbidity
	SDG14: Life below water	River discharge, plastics, water quality, algal blooms, eutrophication status
	SDG15: Life on land	Water quantity, water quality, flood, drought, aquatic plants/vegetations
	SDG16: Peace, justice and strong institutions	Opportunities for exploitation of water related EO-products can be explored
	SDG17: Partnerships for the goals	Opportunities for exploitation of water related EO-products can be explored

	Category	EO variable
GCI s	Temperature and energy	Water temperature, water level, water extent
	Atmospheric composition	Water extent, primary production, Chl-a
	Ocean and water	Water extent, lake colour, water temperature, flood, drought, algal blooms
	Cryosphere	Lake ice extent, lake ice thickness

EO can be a valuable tool for monitoring ECVs on a global scale for inland waters, including surface water temperature (Temperature & Energy); surface water extent and primary productivity for GHG emission estimates (Atmospheric composition); surface water extent, water levels, lake colour, surface water temperature, and algal bloom phenology (Ocean & water); and glaciers and lake ice extent (Cryosphere).

Copernicus Services offer wide-ranging opportunities in support of the SDGs and GCOS especially in data poor countries. Water-related EO products are principally showcased in SDG6 and the UN Environment Programme have accepted the global surface water explorer as default data source for SDG 6.6.1. A future Water focused thematic Hub could address more SDGs and deliver new indicators for achieving them.

8. Links between mission-service application

Around five years ago CEOS (Committee on Earth Observation Satellites) commissioned a study (CEOS, 2018⁹) on the feasibility of designing an Earth observing satellite mission focused on the Aquatic Ecosystem including the biogeochemistry of inland, estuarine, deltaic and near coastal waters as well as mapping macrophytes, macro-algae, sea grasses and coral reefs. They noted that these environments need higher spatial resolution than current and planned ocean colour sensors and need higher spectral resolution than current and planned land Earth observing sensors offer. This includes the topic of this analysis - inland lakes, reservoirs, lagoons, rivers, etc. and they present detailed analysis of characteristics that would be required in a dedicated upstream EO sensor and satellite system. This could be taken into consideration for the future generations of European Sentinels.

Currently, the in-land water sector utilises data from the first 3 Sentinel missions and sensors even if none of these were designed with the water sector's requirements in mind. This is detailed in Annex 3 of D1.3. This utilisation occurs principally through products from five of the available Copernicus Services, and from the Copernicus in-situ data from the EEA. A summary of these can be found in the table below. Only one service, the Copernicus Land Monitoring Service (CLMS) has a defined inland water theme..

Table 3: Summary of the Copernicus products utilised by the water sector

⁹ CEOS 2018. Feasibility Study for an Aquatic Ecosystem Earth Observing System, Arnold Dekker (CSIRO) and Nicole Pinnel (DLR)

Name of Copernicus Service	Product/s relevant to the water sector
<p>Copernicus Land Monitoring Service (CLMS)</p>	<p>The following products are offered under the water CLMS Global component theme:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the water surface temperature and water quality (turbidity, trophic state) of medium and large-sized lakes. • the surface extent covered by water on a permanent basis like lakes, with a seasonal frequency like backwater ponds, or occasional occurrence such as from severe floods. • the water bodies. • the water level of lakes and rivers. <p>Furthermore, the CLMS products are useful for hydrological modelling as well as short- and medium-term meteorological forecasting by providing accurate estimations about the water and heat exchanges between land and atmosphere.</p> <p>The CLMS also offers a free and easy to use online data platform, namely the Freshwater Ecosystem Explorer.</p> <p>Offers information in support of Water Framework Directive, Zero Pollution Strategy, and CAP</p>
<p>Copernicus Emergency Management Service (CEMS)</p>	<p>In Europe, CEMS uses an extensive amount of in-situ data coming from data collection centres involved in the early warning and monitoring for the water sector.</p>

Name of Copernicus Service	Product/s relevant to the water sector
	<p>Two early warning and monitoring floods services, namely the European and Global Flood Awareness Systems (<u>EFAS</u> and <u>GloFAS</u>) are available. They deliver the following water related products:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● medium range probabilistic flood forecasts; ● post processed bias corrected forecasts; ● flash flood indicators with a lead time up to 3 days & radar based flash flood now casting; ● EFAS Flood & Flash Flood Notifications to all partners at river basin level; ● monitoring of national flood alert exceedances; ● soil moisture, snow maps, anomalies; ● hydrological seasonal outlook; ● impact forecasts and pre-tasking of Copernicus EMS rapid mapping. <p>The European and Global Drought Observatories (<u>EDO</u> and <u>GDO</u>). They provide continuous monitoring, forecasting of key drought and heat indicators across Europe and the World and they are serving the EU's Emergency Response Coordination Centre (ERCC) as well as other international stakeholders.</p> <p>Details on the foreseen CEMS Copernicus Evolution can be found in D1.3.</p>

Name of Copernicus Service	Product/s relevant to the water sector
Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S)	<p>C3S offers a number of essential climate variables about the ocean and land in coordination with other services and organisations, such as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • for ocean, variables on sea surface temperature, sea level, sea ice, ocean colour • for land hydrology and cryosphere, variable on lakes, glaciers, ice sheets and ice shelves, soil moisture • seasonal predictions and distributes forecast and hindcast data which are freely available for use and download from C3S servers. <p>The SIS: European Water Service, managed by C3S, is one of the most important services related to water. The Service aims to help a broad range of water managers for water allocation, flood management, ecological status and industrial water use, with information about climate change in water related variables or hydrological seasonal forecasts.</p>
Copernicus Marine Environment Monitoring Service (CMEMS)	<p>CMEMS mainly focuses on ocean and marine ecosystems for the global ocean and the European regional seas, and therefore can support aquaculture applications. However, future plans for updates under Copernicus 2.0 will expand the interfaces between marine and land Copernicus Services. It will include a focus on hydrology/rivers in order to monitor or forecast the major EU rivers by the production of validated river discharges for freshwater input, nutrient loading,</p>

Name of Copernicus Service	Product/s relevant to the water sector
	<p>particulate and dissolved matter. This is a horizontal action between multiple Copernicus Services, marine, land, emergency and climate.</p> <p>CMEMS already provides support to several important policies related to the water sector, such as WFD, MSFD, MSP, Green Deal or Bathing Directive by supplying within its catalogues a series of water quality variables and products.</p>
Copernicus Service for Security	<p>Copernicus Security Service is composed of components, one of which is linked to the water sector, namely the Copernicus Maritime Surveillance (CMS) Service. CMS is implemented by EMSA - European Maritime Safety Agency, and it supports a better understanding and improved monitoring of activities at sea, within a wide range of operational functions such as maritime safety and security, fisheries control, customs, law enforcement, marine environment pollution monitoring, and others.</p>
Copernicus in-situ component (EEA)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Optical data such as lake water reflectances and Inherent Optical Properties (needed for calibrating and validating the atmospheric correction algorithm(s) and optical processes in the water (absorption and scattering). ● Water constituents data relevant for calibrating the in water algorithms as well as validating the derived in water parameters (turbidity, trophic state (chlorophyll

Name of Copernicus Service	Product/s relevant to the water sector
	a), suspended sediment concentrations, cyanobacteria, CDOM, DOC, SPIM, SPOM and others.

Regarding future Sentinel missions, Task 1.3 identified the following future missions as relevant to the inland water domain:

- Sentinel-8 LSTM: Copernicus Land Surface Temperature Monitoring
- Sentinel-9 CRISTAL: Copernicus Polar Ice and Snow Topography Altimeter
- Sentinel-10 CHIME: Copernicus Hyperspectral Imaging Mission
- Sentinel-11 CIMR: Copernicus Imaging Microwave Radiometer
- Sentinel-12 ROSE-L: L-band Synthetic Aperture Radar

How far these missions will go towards meeting the requirements of the water sector, will be elucidated in the Gap Analysis Framework (see last chapter).

The analysis presented in D1.4 - Report with end-user needs and requirements, also highlights the upstream requirements of the water sector through their synthesis of 'Sensor requirements and capabilities'.

These include the following for upstream capabilities:

1. Spatial resolution of 1-5 m
2. Increased resolution (sub 1 m) in order to identify smaller inland water bodies and provide information on the hydromorphology of rivers
3. Spatial resolution 5-20m, pixel resolution to 1 ha minimum mapping unit
4. Time resolution yearly and seasonal maps based on daily to weekly information

5. Ideal inland and near coastal water quality sensor for general use and covering the needs of most applications (imaging spectrometer with 5-8 nm spectral bands from 340 to 1000 nm, and a minimum of three SWIR bands, Spatial resolution: 5-10 m ground sampling distance (GSD), Revisit frequency should be high as possible: daily for reservoirs/dams, and weekly for lakes/ivers, monthly for coastal).

As well as the following capabilities that can be interpreted as midstream capabilities:

6. Integration of radar data and services
7. Integration of spectroradiometers in the existing infrastructures
8. Wider collection of hyperspectral radiometry
9. Hyperspectral data for water quality, algal blooms and shallow water.

This highlights issues that could be taken into account in the further development of the Copernicus Programme. The Copernicus Regulation [377/2014] states that “the evolution of the Copernicus space component should be based on an analysis of options to meet evolving user needs”. It is therefore essential to create a network and governance bringing together the needs of the water community in such a way that a roadmap can be developed as input to the Copernicus evolution programmes (of which the current project is the first step).

A relevant development for the water sector and linked to Copernicus Services is the development of the concept for the Copernicus Thematic Hubs (CTH). The CTH is an initiative to regroup, under one single entry point, information generated by several Copernicus Services for a given high level topic. In order to obtain a rich and operational level of integration it is important to implement for the CTHs the following:

- Collect and maintain in a single catalogue the relevant products and information,
- Harmonise these inputs and provide to users guidance and support with the help of the contributing Copernicus Services.

An important aspect of the concept will be engaging with the specific user communities and increasing their uptake of Copernicus data and products and services. All thematic hubs will start with a 1-year proof-of-concept phase.

The planned establishment of a Copernicus Coastal Thematic Hub (CCTH) under the Copernicus Marine Environment Monitoring Service (CMEMS), in collaboration with several other Copernicus Services and implemented by EU institutions in close collaboration with Member States national authorities, is a very good opportunity for other high level topics (or sectors) to emerge in response to their fragmentation and scattered presence within the Copernicus programme. The establishment of a Copernicus Water Thematic Hub, based on the CCTH analogue, could represent a viable solution for the inland water sector to crystallise under the Copernicus programme.

9. Innovation needs and business opportunities

The market drivers for information on water parameters identified WP 1 (Policies, SDGS, user requirements, technical, research opportunities, etc.) represent business opportunities for the EO industry providing value-added services (VAS). As mentioned in D1.5, more than 93 % of European EO companies are SMEs and start-ups. Through a better understanding of the user requirements and an awareness of the many research opportunities under Horizon Europe and beyond, EO service providers are faced with many opportunities to develop new VAS for the water sector. However, these companies will have to be open to the prospect of collating data from multiple sources, going far beyond just ground-truthed EO data.

The core Copernicus services used by the water sector (e.g. CMEMS, CEMS, CLMS, C3S) provide EO-based information from global to pan-European levels, with some products

available at national and regional levels. This is an outcome of the fact that these EO-based services were put in place to better inform the European Commission when formulating EU policies, security measures, and also to leverage on the vast amount of EO data available. In line with this concept of services for the public good, Copernicus data is made freely available. These geographical information services were also developed as core 'upstream' services that will also allow the private EO sector opportunities to develop 'downstream' applications (at catchment and local levels) that are closer to the market. Since such applications are based on easily accessible, free-of-charge EO data and information (most likely together with contributing and complementary data), this will give EO service providers a commercial advantage. It is the author's view that despite this conceptual model, in reality many EO service providers prefer to start from scratch and use Sentinel data directly for new applications, allowing better tailoring to their information design.

Should the Copernicus Programme of the EC decide to better target the needs of the water sector, this provides the EO industry with a number of opportunities: 1. opportunities to provide image processing and analysis under contract to the Copernicus services for new services aimed at the water sector. 2. EO companies can benefit from the lack of multi-source analytics in conjunction with EO on local, regional level for water managers and public water authorities (who are required to report on Framework Directive parameters to their national level). Although it is not yet clear what measures will be promoted under the new EU Missions Area on "Healthy Oceans, Seas, and Coastal and Inland Waters", this encompasses the inland water sector and ecosystems and is likely to further drive the need for more information on inland water systems.

The seven industry interviews (reported in D1.5) also identified some innovation and business opportunities distributed across the whole EO Value Chain. It showed also that all participants perceive Copernicus as a good or excellent potential for their business or organisations, and that they are either using or planning to use Copernicus services. The

interviews even provided some unanticipated findings such as the willingness to become part of the Copernicus Contributing Missions, or the request for Copernicus Services to be more responsive to a service co-design or co-development approach, with a focus on end-users and pragmatic service KPIs. The interviews also confirmed the growing need of EO service providers for better accuracy and resolution imagery in order to assess or monitor water bodies regardless of scale, or the need of end-users of being provided with actionable information in order to make better decisions. The emergence of very high resolution (VHR) or very very high resolution (VVHR) satellite data, and improved temporal resolution (from constellations of small satellites), will offer the EO industry even more opportunities for application development. They also recognised that there is a need on their part to develop new business models for the aquafarming, insurance and tourism markets, for example.

Moreover, these experts expressed the following requirements which would have positive impact on their business or organisation:

1. Access to very high resolution data from the Copernicus Contributing Missions
2. Become a contributing mission to the Copernicus Contributing Missions
3. More focus from Copernicus and ESA for the co-design and co-develop applications with end-users than only building services
4. Customers request actionable information (dashboards, decision making tools) instead of specialised services
5. Capacity building for end-users
6. Integration with in-situ component
7. Digital transformation using EO
8. Using AI, ML, automation and cloud infrastructure for providing EO solutions.

In D1.5, we identified a strong link between water and the agriculture sector. The use of water for agriculture is one of the largest water markets, and the use of EO for agricultural

monitoring is already a vast, established market. A key opportunity lies in developing EO VAS services for the water component of the agriculture market. Another way of looking at the business opportunities is to keep the economic importance of the user sector in mind, for example the cost of damage due to floods and droughts. This creates a demand for VAS that will help authorities reduce the risk of or avoid such damage. Insurance companies can be targeted with risk and damage assessment information on floods and droughts.

Moreover, business innovation opportunities in the inland water sector are highly influenced by policy and legislative actions within the EU and intergovernmental organizations, which follows from the analysis in D.1.3. Thus, opportunities arise from the EU Space Programme Regulation itself, EU sectoral policies, international treaties, resolutions, and other guiding instruments.

The analysis of the emerging user requirements from within WaterForce, points to ample research and business opportunities in the water sector and for SMEs. In D1.4, a large number of emerging needs have been identified for which innovative products and services can be developed by research projects, existing EO businesses and SMEs, or even spin-off companies. Such developments should use multi-source analytics in conjunction with EO and work towards systems for situational awareness in water management. Ideally, customers would like seamless links between the information from EO, drones, citizen science and in-situ monitoring. This is now enabled by the move to digital technologies and developments in smart sensors, IoT, big data analytics, AI, etc.

The EO industry can also benefit from research and innovation projects on new EO technologies and applications to create spin-off companies or to scaling-up of commercial activities of existing companies. Numerous EO service providers have started with developing proof of concept studies based on Copernicus Services (e.g. CMEMS, CLMS, EMS) or Sentinel data, and/or using DIAS infrastructure to offer solutions to their clients

and meet the demand for products and VAS for water sector end-users. Some examples of these are:

- Planetek Italia with its services to the aquaculture sector with Rheticus® AquaculturePlus).
- GeoVillle GmbH which has grown from a startup to an established EO company with global presence through the provision of Copernicus services and large EU funded RIA projects.
- WaterInsight NL. WaterInsight have successfully integrated EO with their in-house sensors (in-situ data) through EU research funding and innovation grants. For example Their EOMORES service is a commercial spin-off of a EU funded project which provides user-tailored solutions for monitoring the quality of inland and coastal water bodies.

In conclusion, the overall size of the water market and the move towards smart water management indicates vast opportunities for EO service providers. This is further reinforced by the general evolution of the EO value adding services (VAS) market from technology push to market pull and an increasing demand from different user groups for water applications. Clearly, there is a gap in data and information for water management, and serve to inform the 'value of water' (See Water Force report 2017).

10. Conclusions and recommendations to the Roadmap

Information provided in market and trend reports available for Space and EO imply that the role of EO in the water sector is currently limited to a few specific applications, but currently there is no specifically identified EO market for water. Most of the time this market is hidden or segmented underneath other market sectors (e.g. agriculture, natural

resources, emergency). This could be due to the fact that Water is a transversal sector on which many other sectors rely or exist. However, the definition of a future EO inland water service can lead to a better representation within the existing market taxonomy for EO data and services focusing on the water sector.

The use of Copernicus for water management can be potentially driven by EU and international policies, which comprises a plethora of instruments with varying legal standing. The great majority of law texts do not specify the use of EO data as a method to accomplish the aims of improving certain water-related sectors. However, documents providing policy actions or recommendations promote EO data as a viable technology for relevant applications. Thus, the uses of Copernicus can be determined by policy makers. At the same time, there is no need to describe specific techniques to accomplish one or more results in the field of inland water management: on the contrary, general formulations such as, for instance, the demand for monitoring or mapping measures already entail the use of space technologies, and hence, Copernicus.

Inland water is not defined within the primary objectives of the current or future Sentinel missions. As mentioned above, the EO sector currently uses a number of components of the Copernicus services that are relevant for water applications, and leverages on the current capabilities of the Sentinel payloads. This could be rectified by either defining the requirements for a future water mission¹⁰, and increasing the current Copernicus Services capabilities with more Copernicus Contributing Missions to respond to the inland water sector challenges and provide access to it. Currently there is no Copernicus service that directly serves the inland water sector. Instead inland water products and services can be found within five out of six core services, namely: CLMS, CEMS, C3S, CMEMS, and Copernicus Service for Security, but clearly these data sources are scattered and none of

¹⁰ The discussion about the development of an inland water mission from deliverable D1.3 showed that there are no provisions, for the following two decades, to launch a dedicated Sentinel mission. This is based on the fact that there is no Earth Explorer planned for inland water until 2035. Moreover, a Sentinel mission is based in general on the success of a ten year Earth Explorer.

them were specifically designed to meet the requirements of the water sector. Thus it was suggested this could be addressed by the establishment of a digital hub for inland water. Such a hub should collect and maintain a single inland water catalogue with relevant products and information, based on harmonised inputs from water users. Furthermore, such a future dedicated inland water hub can address more SDGs (see D1.6) and provide new indicators for achieving the SDGs. In this way, the industry request for Copernicus Services to be more responsive to a service co-design or co-development approach, with a focus on end-users and pragmatic service KPIs, can also be achieved.

In conclusion, from the analysis carried out in WP1, we suggest the creation of a dedicated thematic Water Hub or platform which seamlessly collates data and information from a wide range of sources - EO, in-situ & citizen science, short-range remote sensing, drones, etc. Unlike the Copernicus services with their focus on EO, such a platform could put more emphasis on multi-source analytics to meet the user demand for situational awareness in water management. This could be supported by public programmes (like Copernicus and the EEA) in collaboration with the private sector. A model similar to the Copernicus core services could be adopted, whereby 'upstream' water information is produced with public funding while leaving opportunities for industry to use this information free-of-charge to develop water applications and VAS that have commercial value. This delineation of roles could also be based on geo-scale and multi-source data, with the public 'Copernicus type' service offering pan-European, national and in some cases regional products while industry can focus on more local to catchment offerings.

WP1 suggest that the following activities and options be considered in the development of the Roadmap:

1. Expand the user requirements analysis to more representatives of the private water management sector, and from the mining and industry sectors. Gain a better understanding of the requirements of a water-smart society and the Water-Oriented Living Labs (identified in 24 European countries).

2. Use the gap analysis framework to indicate where future Sentinels and Copernicus services should be augmented to meet the technical requirements of all user groups (including water practitioners, EC policies and SDGs) as far as possible.
3. Strong consideration of the requirements for in-situ information coming from the EEA (e.g. for lakes, river level monitoring, inflow data to coastal zones, river level monitoring networks and the use of CS data for calibration/validation (cal-val) of satellite EO water quality products), and from water managers in the public and private sectors.
4. Future research and development activities for the development of new services towards the water market, must insist on multi-source information and the use of smart technologies.
5. Emphasise the role of EO service providers in the expansion of the market for water information and any digital, thematic hub or platform tailored to the inland water sector.
6. Launch an awareness campaign towards private companies in the water sector (non-EO) and those responsible for water monitoring, regarding the capabilities of EO and Copernicus.
7. Suggest the creation of a dedicated thematic Water Hub or platform which seamlessly collates data and information from a wide range of sources - EO, in-situ & citizen science, short-range remote sensing, drones, etc. Such a platform should put more emphasis on multi-source analytics to meet the user demand for situational awareness in water management. To avoid the risk that this concept becomes too EO heavy, perhaps it should not be labelled a 'Copernicus service'
8. Completion of the spreadsheets in the Gap Analysis Framework should highlight gaps where EO and Copernicus could further support the information requirements of the water sector.

11. Framework to identify gaps between EO and user requirements

The user requirements collated under this project have already been presented in D1.4, and prioritised in D1.5 (according to the number of times it was requested). We have developed a framework to give a high-level overview of how these requirements can be met by EO and Copernicus data and services, either alone or with complementary data from drones, in-situ and citizen science (CS). These we have laid out in 3 spreadsheets – one for the user sector requirements, one for EU policy requirements and one for the SDG parameters.

We used an House of Quality methodology¹¹ (taken from filestage.io) adapted for our purposes. Each user requirement is translated into functional requirements (e.g. spatial and temporal resolutions, sensors, archive data, revisit times, etc.), and then an assessment is made (by experts in the team) to what extent the requirement can be met by EO/Sentinels, contributing missions, and Copernicus services. This is expressed as a percentage reflecting the fit-for-purpose rating of EO and Copernicus at meeting each requirement. The aim of this exercise is to highlight gaps i.e. where EO and current Copernicus services do not currently meet the requirement, and also how the planned evolution of the Sentinels will fare. In a further analysis, the contribution of complementary technologies like in-situ, drones, CS (citizen science) and modelling is assessed with regard to meeting these requirements.

We are aware that by simplifying the detailed functional requirements some complexity related to the EO technical requirements will be lost (e.g. spectral bands etc.), nevertheless

¹¹ The House of Quality (HOQ) is defined as a product planning matrix that is built to show how customer requirements relate directly to the ways and methods companies can use to achieve those requirements.

this analysis should give a good synthesis of a complex set of demand drivers for information and user requirements collated by this project.

These spreadsheets can be found at [HoQ Synthesis vs2](#). WP1 has prepared this framework and we request that these tables are completed by the experts (with their more detailed technical knowledge) from the team.

Once the spreadsheets have been completed, the gaps in EO information sources should be elucidated for:

- User requirements coming from the interviews (D1.4)
- Information requirements derived from EU policies related to water
- Information requirements derived from SDGs related to water

Without pre-empting the outcomes of this analysis, we can recall a number of gaps that have already been identified in D1.5:

1. The user requirements analysis does not sufficiently represent the requirements for water quantity monitoring, nor the requirements of the mining and manufacturing industry.
2. It has already been pointed out that no EU policy requires the use of EO (see D1.2), but that EO and Copernicus can be a key data source for many of the Directives related to water.
3. D1.6 also highlights the relevance of EO capabilities towards achieving the SDG targets by 2030, and demonstrates the need for broad spatial scale and fine temporal resolution global monitoring of inland waters to achieve the SDGs.

